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Research Paper

Computational Docking Study of Phytochemicals Isolated from *Barleria Albostellata* C.B Clarke

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ABSTRACT

Alzheimer disease (AD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disease results in death of brain cells. It causes memory loss and cognitive decline. The symptoms are mild at first and become more severe overtime. Many phytochemicals have been isolated from medicinal plants with anti- alzheimer activity. To perform molecular docking studies of the isolated compound on Alzheimer target protein using Autodock® software Version 1.5.6. Evaluation of molecular docking analysis of isolated phytoconstituents from methanolic extracts of *Barleria albostellata* whole plant phytoconstituents such as Carbamic Acid, Eicosanoic Acid, 9 Oxononanoic Acid, Heptafluorobutyric Acid, Pentadecanoic Acid, Sulphurous Acid were docked with anti-alzheimer drug target proteins such as acetylcholinesterase using Autodock 4.2 software. Heptafluorobutyric acid (-6.58 Kcal/mol) has significant bind energy with acetylcholinesterase when compared with standard. Remaining phytoconstituents such as carbamic acid, eicosanoic acid, 9 oxononanoic acid, pentadecanoic acid, sulphurous acid showed moderate to less binding affinity with target proteins

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INTRODUCTION

Molecular docking is a crucial aspect of computer-aided drug design (CADD) technique to study how a small molecule (ligand/drug) interacts with a macromolecule (protein/enzyme, DNA, etc.). Molecular docking basically addresses three key goals - virtual screening, pose prediction, and binding affinity estimation.¹ Docking is performed using free or licensed molecular docking software such as Autodockvina, PyRx, CCDC GOLD, Schrodinger, MOE, GLIDE, among others provide varied approaches to simulate these interactions. By retrieving protein structures from the PDB, researchers can analyze how different compounds interact with specific enzymes, aiming to find the most energetically favorable configuration for a ligand-enzyme complex.² This process helps in understanding potential interactions between molecules, aiding drug design and discovery. Docking serves as a crucial tool in rational drug design by predicting how small molecule candidates bind to protein targets. A statistical scoring function translates interacting energy into numerical docking scores, offering insights into the strength of molecular interactions. This process aids in assessing the affinity and activity of potential drugs within the body.

Docking is most used in the field of drug design and docking is applied to:

- Hit identification: Docking with a scoring function efficiently screens drug databases *in silico* to identify molecules likely to bind to a specific protein target.
- Lead optimization: Docking predicts the ligand's binding orientation to a protein, aiding in the design of more potent and selective analogs based on this information.
- Bioremediation: Protein-ligand docking predicts enzyme interactions degrading pollutants, aiding in identifying potential

biodegradation pathways for environmental cleanup efforts.³

The primary aim of this study was to determine the optimal positions and orientations for ligands within the enzyme or receptor's binding center. It also aimed to assess the impact of isolated phytoconstituents from *Barleria albostellata* on their antialzheimer properties. Material and Methods

1. Docking software

Among the different types of software's available for docking, it used the Autodock4.2 software for the molecular docking investigation of proteins involved in anti-alzheimer Activity.⁴⁻⁹

2. Phytoconstituents / Ligands

The Ligands were collected from an article published by Manohar Reddy and his co-workers (2022). Phytoconstituents or ligands like Carbamic Acid, Pentadecanoic Acid, Eicosanoic Acid, 9 Oxononanoic Acid, Heptafluorobutyric Acid and Sulphurous Acid were used for molecular docking studies.¹⁰

3. Potential targets and binding sites

The 3D structures of antialzheimer drug targets such as acetylcholinesterase are obtained from protein database bank. Based on these ligands in crystallized structures the active sites in receptors were determined.⁴⁻⁹

4. Docking

Docking was executed to acquire probable conformations and positions for the ligand-receptor complexes at the binding site. Binding site was determined using the previous knowledge of the original ligand's interaction site. For the stimulation runs, each ligand was kept flexible, but

the amino acid residues of active site were kept rigid and default parameters values were taken. Alzheimer targets for various proteins were selected based on the literature survey. The structures of all the receptors were obtained from PDB format. Docking studies were performed against acetylcholinesterase using Autodock 4.2 software with isolated phytoconstituents and standard Rivastigmine as ligands. The results obtained in the form of binding energy and amino acids interactions by hydrogen bonding.¹⁰⁻¹¹

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In silico methods are computer-based methods widely used in the pharmacological field of science to help discover inhibitors with high binding capabilities with a protein target. *In silico* methods have been used to create various inhibitors for a spectrum of diseases. Molecular Docking is an important method in molecular biology and computeraided drug design. Ligand-protein docking helps predict the binding mode of a Ligand and Protein of known 3-dimensional structures. Evaluation of molecular docking

analysis of isolated phytoconstituents from methanolic extracts of *Barleria albostellata* whole plant phytoconstituents such as Carbamic Acid, Eicosanoic Acid, 9 Oxononanoic Acid, Heptafluorobutyric Acid, Pentadecanoic Acid, Sulphurous Acid were docked with antialzheimer drug target proteins such acetyl choline esterase using Autodock 4.2 software. The binding energy of phytoconstituents from methanolic extracts of *Barleria albostellata* whole plant such as Carbamic Acid, Pentadecanoic Acid, Eicosanoic Acid, 9 Oxononanoic Acid, Heptafluorobutyric Acid and Sulphurous Acid with acetyl choline esterase was found to be -4.65, -4.89, -4.92, -4.21, 6.58 and -5.48 Kcal/mol. Heptafluorobutyric acid was interaction with 10 amino acids. Heptafluorobutyric acid (-6.58 Kcal/mol) has significant bind energy with acetylcholine esterase when compared with standard Rivastigmine (-10.56Kcal/mol) (Table.1&2 and Figure.1&2). Methanolic extracts of *Barleria albostellata* whole plant phytoconstituent such Heptafluorobutyric acid has highly bind with acetyl choline esterase and inhibited it to possess the antialzheimer activity.

Table.1: Phytoconstituents of Barleria albostellata docking with acetyl cholinesterase

S.No	Phytoconstituents	Docking binding Energy (Kcal/mol)	Amino acid interaction
1	Carbamic acid	-4.65	Phe 155 Val 236 Val 293 Ser 291
2	Pentadecanoic acid	4.89	Val 293 Val 236 Phe 155
3	Eicosanoic acid	-4.92	Asn 65 Ser 125 Asn 66
			Phe 155

4	9 Oxononanoic acid	-4.21	Ser 291 Val 236 Val 293
5	Heptafluorobutyric acid	-6.58	Asn 65 Asn 66 Cys 67 Pro 64 Cys 94 Tyr 116 Gly 123 Ser 124 Ser 125 Ser 147
6	Sulphurous acid	-5.48	Asn 65 Asn 66 Cys 67 Ser 125

1. Sulphurous acid

3D Structure

2D Structure

Docking binding Energy (Kcal/mol)

2. Carbamic acid

3D Structure

2D Structure

Docking binding Energy (Kcal/mol)

3. Pentadecanoic acid

3D Structure

2D Structure

Docking binding Energy (Kcal/mol)

4. Eicosanoic acid

3DStructure

2D Structure

Docking binding Energy (Kcal/mol)

5. Heptafluorobutyric acid

3D Structure 2D Structure

Docking binding Energy (Kcal/mol)

6. 9 Oxononanoic acid

3D Structure 2D Structure

Docking binding Energy (Kcal/mol)

Table.2: Standard drug Rivastigmine docking with acetyl cholinesterase

S.No	Ligand	Docking binding Energy (Kcal/mol)	Aminoacid interaction
1	Rivastigmine	-10.56	Ala377 Gln527 Leu380 His381 Phe531

Fig.2 3D,2D structure and binding energy of Rivastigmine docking with acetyl cholinesterase

Docking binding Energy (Kcal/mol)

CONCLUSION

Among the in-silico docking study for isolated phytoconstituents from methanolic extracts of *Barleria albobellata* whole plant phytoconstituents such as Carbamic Acid, Eicosanoic Acid, 9 Oxononanoic Acid, Heptafluorobutyric Acid, Pentadecanoic Acid, Sulphurous Acid were docked with antialzheimer drug target proteins such acetyl choline esterase using Autodock4.2 software. Heptafluorobutyric Acid (-6.58 Kcal/mol) has significant bind energy with acetyl choline esterase when compared with standard Rivastigmine (-10.56Kcal/mol). This efforts will choose for further study and chemical synthesis as anti-alzheimer drugs for the management of Alzheimer. In future it may lead to the development of Heptafluorobutyric acid agonists for anti- alzheimer activity

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